

A new genus of small Vetigastropoda from eastern Atlantic Ocean and Indo-Pacific islands and seamounts

Un nuevo género de pequeños Vetigastropoda de islas y montes submarinos del Océano Atlántico oriental y del Indo-Pacífico

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ABSTRACT

The gross anatomy of "*Tinostoma*" *azorica* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896 is described for the first time, from specimens collected on the Galicia Bank, NW Spain. On the basis of this information and of the already known data regarding the radula and the operculum, the new genus *Seamountiella* n. gen. is proposed for this species, and tentatively placed in the family Skeneidae (Vetigastropoda, Trochoidea). *Seamountiella* is compared with the fossil genera *Ataphrus* Gabb, 1869, *Falsataphrus* Gründel, 2000 and *Leucodiscus* Cossmann, 1918, and with *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877, the only Recent genus in Skeneidae having the columellar callus partially or completely covering the umbilicus. In addition, three new species of *Seamountiella*, from the north-eastern Atlantic seamounts, from Mayotte Island and from the Plateau des Chesterfield in New Caledonia are described.

RESUMEN

Se describe por vez primera la anatomía externa de "*Tinostoma*" *azorica* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896, a partir de ejemplares recolectados en el Banco de Galicia, NW España. En base a ello y a resultados obtenidos previamente sobre rádula y opérculo, se describe un nuevo género *Seamountiella* n. gen., tentativamente asignado a la familia Skeneidae (Vetigastropoda, Trochoidea). Se comparan los caracteres morfológicos de su concha con los de los géneros fósiles *Ataphrus* Gabb, 1869, *Falsataphrus* Gründel, 2000 y *Leucodiscus* Cossmann, 1918 y también con los del género *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877, único género actual de los Skeneidae en el cual el ombligo está parcial o totalmente cubierto por un callo. Además, se describen tres especies nuevas de *Seamountiella* de las montañas submarinas del NE Atlántico, de la Isla de Mayotte y del Plateau des Chesterfield, en Nueva Caledonia.

INTRODUCTION

"*Tinostoma*" *azorica* was described by DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896) from the bathyal level of the Azores, and its generic placement was based on the smooth and lenticular shell with a callus covering

totally the umbilicus. RUBIO & ROLÁN (2009) studied the radula and operculum of specimens from Galicia Bank and found that this species has a rhipidoglossate radula, typical of the Vetigastropoda, the-

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refore questioning its placement in the family Tornidae Sacco, 1896 (Caenogastropoda: Truncatelloidea).

Material from several deep-sea cruises in the North Atlantic and in the Indo-Pacific region provided more material of this and other similar species. The purpose of this paper is to redescribe "*Tinostoma*" *azorica*, to discuss its affinities with other fossil and Recent genera of similar appearance, and propose a new genus for that species. Additionally three new species, one from the north-eastern Atlantic, one from the Indian Ocean and one from the Pacific Ocean, considered as congeneric, are described.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied was collected in the following expeditions:

French oceanographic expeditions carried out by Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris (MNHN):

SEAMOUNT 1 (1987) on board R.V. 'Le Noroit', to the lusitanian seamounts Gorringe, Josephine, Lion, Seine, Ampère and Galicia Bank. Drawings of living animals were prepared on board whenever possible.

SEAMOUNT 2 (1993) on board R.V. 'Le Suroit', to Great Meteor, Hyères, Irving-Cruiser, Plato, Atlantis, Tyro and Antialtair seamounts in the north-eastern Atlantic.

BENTHEDI (1977) on board R.V. 'Le Suroit', N.E. of the Mozambique Channel (Glorieuses islands, Geyser Bank, Zélée Bank, Mayotte Island).

EBISCO (2005) on board R.V. 'Alis' to the seamounts South of the Chesterfield Islands.

Spanish oceanographic expedition carried out by Spanish Oceanographic Institute (IEO):

INDEMARES-BANGAL 0711 (2011) on board R.V. 'Miguel Oliver', expedition to Galicia Bank.

In the above-mentioned surveys, the coarse fractions, usually above 10 mm, were mostly sorted on board to phyla, then sorted to species level in the lab. The finer fractions were preserved on board, and later sieved on 5, 2, 1, and 0.5

mm sieves, and sorted under a stereomicroscope.

Spanish oceanographic expeditions carried out by the Marine Biology Station of A Graña (EBMG) of the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC):

SARRIDAL (2007) on board R.V. 'Sarridal' and A SELVA (2008) on board R.V. 'Sarmiento de Gamboa', both targeted to sample the bathyal bottoms of carbonated crusts in the fishing ground known as A Selva (NW de Galicia).

DIVA-ARTABRIA II (2009) on board R.V. 'Hesperides', targeted to study the biodiversity of the deep bathyal bottoms of the west coast of Galicia, including Quiniela Bank, Sea do Crime and the western slope of Galicia, between 200-3200 m.

Empty shells, which constitute most of the material, are preserved dry, and only a limited number of live-collected specimens are preserved in ethanol. Adult shells and juveniles were distinguished in the counts, those shells treated as juveniles having a fragile, cutting edge of the outer lip as opposed to the rounded edge of adult shells, and are usually also distinctly smaller than adults.

Shells were photographed using a Nikon DXM camera mounted on a stereomicroscope, taking a series of views focused in distinct planes which were assembled using CombineZ software (HADLEY, 2006). The SEM micrographs were made in a Quanta 200 and AVO in the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico of the University of Santiago de Compostela (CACTUS) and Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) of the University of Vigo. The radula was obtained in dry material dissolving the soft parts in Sodium hydroxide.

Abbreviations

IEO Spanish Institute of Oceanography
EBMG Marine Biology Station of A Graña, Ferrol
MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris
Stn Station (collecting locality)
s empty shell
spm live taken specimen, with soft parts
jv juvenile

SYSTEMATICS

Subclass VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1980

Superfamily TROCHOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815

Family SKENEIDAE W. Clark, 1851

Seamountiella n. gen.

Type species: *Tinostoma azorica* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896.

Etymology: The genus name is derived from the name of the oceanographic expeditions carried out by MNHN in the north-eastern Atlantic during the years 1987 and 1993.

Diagnosis: Shell solid, smooth and very shiny. Spire depressed, with flattened apex; periphery and base convex. Protoconch of 0.75 whorl, smooth. Teleoconch with an initial phase of 0.5 to 2 whorls, in which the whorl diameter increases slowly and there are marked growth lines, and a final phase of 1.1 to 2 whorls, in which the diameter of the whorl increases more rapidly. Umbilicus covered by columellar callus even in juvenile stage. Aperture rounded, slightly

prosocline; columella arched; outer lip thin, smooth edge.

Animal with rounded snout, not bilobed; cephalic and epipodial tentacles papillate; four epipodial tentacles on each side, with tuberculiform sensory organs at the base; propodial penis not observed.

Radula with five lateral teeth; innermost marginal tooth forming a latero-marginal plate.

Operculum horny, thin, multispiral, concave.

Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figures 1A-C, 2, 3A-F, 4A-C)

Tinostoma azorica Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896: 485, pl. 21, figs. 16-18 [Type locality: Azores Islands, Pr. Alice, Stn 46, 1385 m - Stn 117, 2102 m]; LOCARD, 1898: 10-11.

Tinostoma azoricum (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896): GOFAS, LE RENARD & BOUCHET (2001): 190; BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006): 70; HOFFMANN & FREIWALD (2017): 69, 75.

Material examined (59 spm, 929 s): Galicja Bank, INDEMARES BANGAL 0711: 27 spm, 406 s, Stn V2, 43°00.1'N, 11°57.6'W/43°00.6'N, 11°57.2'W, 1706-1750 m; 2 spm, 44 s, Stn V5, 42°56.8'N, 11°58.5'W/42°57.2'N, 11°58.3'W, 1631-1640 m; 16 spm, 60 s, Stn V10, 42°41.9'N, 11°26.7'W/42°42.4'N, 11°26.9'W, 1720-1723 m. SEAMOUNT 1: 6 spm and 76 s, Stn DW108, 42°50.9'N, 11°53.1'W, 1110-1125 m; 2 spm, Stn DW116, 42°52.4'N, 11°50.6'W, 985-1000 m. North-west of Spain, DIVA ARTABRIA II: 1 s, Stn 15EBS, G 1267-1286 m; 1 spm, Stn 18EBS, Golfo Ártabro, Galicia, Spain; 1 spm, Stn 31EBS, 773-862 m. – A SELVA: 7 s, Stn DRN7, 44°11.65'N, 08°58.15'W, 908-1106 m; 4 s, Stn DRN7c, 44°08.65'N, 08°55.30'W, 566-581 m. North Atlantic seamounts, SEAMOUNT 2. – Great Meteor Bank: 1 spm, Stn DW152, 30°02.0'N, 28°22.1'W, 470 m. – Hyères Bank: 10 s, Stn DW185, 31°25.5'N, 28°51.8'W, 1250 m; 2 s, Stn DW186, 31°26.1'N, 28°51.8'W, 1520 m; 6 s, Stn DW192, 31°27.9'N, 28°59.1'W, 750 m; 10 s, Stn DW200, 31°19.1'N, 28°36.0'W, 1060 m 1 s, Stn DW202, 31°16.5'N, 28°43.1'W, 640 m; 2 spm, 144 s (60 jv), Stn DW203, 31°09.5'N, 28°43.5'W, 845 m. – Irving Bank: 1 s, Stn DW231, 32°01.5'N, 27°54.5'W, 745 m; 62 s, Stn DW238, 32°17.3'N, 27°32.3'W, 890 m. – Plato Bank: 1 spm, 86 s, Stn DW242, 33°11.48'N, 28°57.0'W, 710 m. – Atlantis Bank: 9 s, Stn DW261, 34°22.40'N, 30°27.80'W, 1340 m.

Description: Shell small (up to 4.5 mm), solid, smooth; spire depressed, with a flattened apex, formed by 3.5-4.0 whorls se-

parated by a weakly marked suture. Shell white, shiny with the subsutural and basal callus area more opaque.

Figure 1. *Seamountiella azorica* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896); same specimen as Figure 2, 4.0 mm diameter, Galicia Bank, SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108, 1110-1125 m.

Figura 1. Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896); mismo ejemplar que la Figura 2, diámetro 4,0 mm, Banco de Galicia, SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108, 1110-1125 m.

The protoconch has 0.75 whorl, is smooth and measures between 260 and 290 μm in maximum diameter. The teleoconch has up to 3.25 whorls, very convex at the periphery; the last whorl occupies about 97% of the total height of the shell. Two differentiated growth phases can be observed: one initial phase of 1.5 to 2.0 whorls in which the diameter of whorls increases slowly and there are marked growth lines, and a second phase, of about 1.25 whorls, where the diameter increases more rapidly, with much more subtle growth lines which can be seen on the base, around the umbilical callus and close to the suture; this change in growth pattern results in an oval, rather than rounded, contour in apical view of adult shells. Umbilicus covered by a callus, except for a small parietal perforation.

Aperture rounded, slightly prosocline, with a fold inside the inner lip on which the operculum abuts; columella

arched, thin, not reflected; outer lip not thickened, with smooth, rounded edge.

Dimensions: the largest shell examined measures 4.5 mm in maximum diameter.

External anatomy (Fig. 2): Snout (sn) long and rounded at the tip. Cephalic lappets absent. Cephalic tentacles (cpt) long, slender and papillate. Eye-lobes placed at the base of cephalic tentacles. Neck lobes (nkl) with smooth edge. Four papillate epipodial tentacles (ept) on each side of the foot, the first nearly as long as the cephalic tentacle, the others shorter and narrower. All epipodial tentacles with a small, knob-like epipodial sense organ (eso) at their base. Propodial penis not seen. Foot truncated anteriorly, rounded posteriorly, with a large propodium.

Radula (Fig. 3D-E) rhipidoglossate with formula N.5.1.5.N, bilaterally symmetrical with regularly arched rows of teeth, all of them with denticulate cusps,

Figure 2. *Seamountiella azorica* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), living animal from Galicia Bank, SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108. (Abbreviations: cpt, cephalic tentacle; ept, epipodial tentacle; eso, epipodial sensory organ; eye, eye; ft, foot; nkl, neck lobe; op, operculum; sn, snout).

Figura 2. Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), animal viviente del Banco de Galicia, SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108. (Abreviaturas: cpt, tentáculo cefálico; ept, tentáculo epipodial; eso, órgano sensorial epipodial; eye, ojo; ft, pié; nkl, lóbulo del cuello; op, opérculo; sn, morro).

strongly bent forward in their upper part.

Central tooth with very broad basal plate, with rounded sides; shaft narrow and sturdy in its central part, with flattened expansions on each side; cusp triangular with a pointed central denticle and 3-4 smaller denticles on each side; the base is concave so as to accommodate the base of the following tooth. Lateral teeth similar in shape to a half of the central tooth; cusps asymmetrical, longer on the outer side with 6-8 denticles and serrated appearance. Marginal teeth very long and narrow, with a long, narrow shaft; cutting edge with a central cusp and 5-6 sharp denticles on each side, giving a serrated appearance; a thin lateromarginal plate is observed at the base of the inner marginal tooth.

Operculum (Fig. 3F) horny, thin, concave, multispiral with central nucleus, yellowish.

Distribution and bathymetric range: Azores Islands, 1385-2012 m (DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896); W Morocco, 912-2210 m and N of the Azores at 4060 m (LOCARD, 1898); Galicia Bank, bathyal bottoms with presence of coral *Lophelia pertusa*, 1110-1750 m depth; Lusitanian seamounts Seine, Ampère and Gettys-

burg (BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD, 2006) and Seamounts of north eastern Ocean Atlantic (Atlantis Bank, Grand Meteor Bank, Irving Bank and Plato Bank), 470-1340 m (this study). SYSOEV (2014) summarized the previously known distribution and bathymetric range from published sources.

Discussion: RUBIO & ROLÁN (2009), on the basis of the radular morphology, considered that "*Tinostoma*" *azoricum* is not actually a member of *Teinostoma* H. & A. Adams, 1853. Based on the similarity of its radula with that of *Skenea serpuloides* (Montagu, 1808) and *Dikoleps cutleriana* (Clark, 1849), the presence of a multispiral operculum with central nucleus and the absence of nacre, they suggested that the species could be placed in Skeneinae (now Skeneidae) Clark, 1851 (Vetigastropoda: Trochoidea). They did not transfer the species to any genus within Skeneinae and conditioned to a further anatomical study the definitive generic placement of that species. The observation of live collected specimens from the Galicia Bank, with papillose cephalic and epipodial tentacles, epipodial sense organs next to the epipodial tentacles, together with the rhipidoglossate radula and the lack of nacre, support this familial placement.

Figure 3. *Seamountiella azorica* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) from Galicia Bank. A: shell, 3.2 mm in diameter, Galicia Bank; B: detail of the small parietal perforation next to the umbilical callus; C: protoconch; D, E: radula; F: operculum (all from INDEMARES-BANGAL 0711 Stn V2, 1706-1750 m, except D, from SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108, 1110-1125 m).

Figura 3. Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A: concha, 3,2 mm de diámetro, Banco de Galicia; B: detalle de la diminuta perforación al lado del callo umbilical; C: protoconcha; D, E: rádula; F: opérculo (todos de INDEMARES-BANGAL 0711 Stn V2, 1706-1750 m, salvo D, de SEAMOUNT 1, Stn DW108, 1110-1125 m).

Figure 4. *Seamountiella azorica* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). Apical views of three shells showing the protoconch/teleoconch limit (small arrows) and the end of the phase of slow increase in diameter (large arrowheads). All from Atlantis Bank, SEAMOUNT 2 Stn DW261, 1340 m.

Figura 4. *Seamountiella azorica* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). Vista apical de tres conchas mostrando el límite protoconchal/teleoconcha (flechas pequeñas) y el final de la fase de aumento lento de diámetro (puntas de flecha grandes). Todos del Banco Atlantis, SEAMOUNT 2 Stn DW261, 1340 m.

By its general appearance (shell solid, smooth; umbilicus covered by a columellar callus; a fold inside the inner lip), "*Tinostoma*" *azorica* resembles the fossil genera *Ataphrus* Gabb, 1869, *Falsataphrus* Gründel, 2000 and *Leucodiscus* Cossmann, 1918, and the Recent genus *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877, the latter the

only Recent skeneid genus in which the umbilicus is also covered by a callus. *Ataphrus* and *Falsataphrus* occur in the Jurassic, and *Leucodiscus* only from the Eocene to the Oligocene.

According to GRÜNDEL & KAIM (2006) and GRÜNDEL (2008) both *Ataphrus* and *Falsataphrus* are diagnosed

Table 1. A comparison of *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877 and *Seamountiella* n. gen., based on observations in *C. romettensis* and *S. azorica*.

Tabla 1. Una comparación de *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877 y *Seamountiella* n. gen., basada en observaciones sobre *C. romettensis* y *S. azorica*.

	<i>Cirsonella</i> Angas, 1877	<i>Seamountiella</i> n. gen.
Protoconch form	Bulbous	Nearly flat
Protoconch ornamentation	Finely spirally striated	Smooth
Protoconch maximum diameter	250-300 µm	260-290 µm
Fold inside the inner lip	Present	Present
Umbilical callus: Adult shell	Present	Present
Umbilical callus: Young shell	Absent	Present
Radula formula	N.4-5.1.4-5.N	N.5.1.5.N
Central tooth	Smooth or slightly serrated, horizontal ridge	Distinctly serrated, no distinct horizontal ridge
Lateromarginal plate	Present	Present
Operculum	Flat	Concave
Operculum ends	Slowly tapering over 1/3 whorl	with oblique edge covering 1/20 whorl

by the morphology of the aperture and peristome. In both genera the columellar callus covers completely the umbilicus only in the adults, while in the juveniles the umbilicus is partially or totally open (GRÜNDEL & KAIM, 2006: fig 9G). Conversely, in *Seamountiella* the umbilicus is covered by a columellar callus even in juvenile stages less than half the size of the adults. *Leucodiscus* differs from *Seamountiella* by having a periumbilical disc with a false umbilicus (i.e., a narrow perforation in the center of the disc) and the columellar callus not extending over the disc but stopping when it reaches the false umbilicus.

The common European species *Cirsonella romettensis* (Granata-Grillo, 1877) is morphologically very close to the type species *C. australis* Angas, 1877 (= *C. weldii* Tenison-Woods, 1877). In adult specimens of *C. romettensis*, a thick columellar callus covers the umbilicus, whereas young specimens lack the thickened inner lip, and have a deep suture and strong spiral cords inside the umbilicus. HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALEYE (2008: 47, fig. 27-28) illustrated for comparison, an adult specimen of *C. romettensis* with the callus completely covering the umbilical area and another one where the umbilicus is only partially covered.

Similarities and differences between *Seamountiella* n. gen. and *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877 are summarized on Table 1.

The radula of *Cirsonella romettensis* was described by WARÉN (1992: 159; 219, fig. 12) as having a smooth central tooth with a distinct horizontal central ridge. There is a correspondence in the radula of our specimens with those figured by Warén; however a weakly pointed cusp with some denticles can be seen on our specimens (Fig. 5 B-D) which may represent an intraspecific variation or else have been eroded on the radula illustrated by Warén (1992). The central tooth in *Cirsonella romettensis* is quite different from that of *Seamountiella*, presenting a distinct horizontal ridge and lacking the characteristic shaft of the latter with a shape recalling a cobra's head. A quite similar radula, albeit without the laterally expanded shaft in the central tooth, was illustrated by HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990: 43; 46, fig. 16) for *Spiromoelleria quadrae* (Dall, 1897) in the subfamily Colloniinae (now family Colloniidae), and qualified as the "least specialized turbinid type". The radula and closed umbilicus in adult specimens of *Seamountiella* also resemble members of the genus *Margarella* Thiele, 1893 (see ZELAYA, 2004), but there the shell is larger, with a more elevated

Figure 5. *Cirsonella romettensis* (Granata-Grillo, 1877) from Galicia Bank. A: shell, 2.11 mm in height; B-D: radula; E: operculum (all from INDEMARES-BANGAL 0711, Stn V2, 1706-1750 m).

Figura 5. *Cirsonella romettensis* (Granata-Grillo, 1877) del Banco de Galicia. A: concha, 2,11 mm de altura; B-D: rádula; E: opérculo (todos de INDEMARES-BANGAL 0711, Stn V2, 1706-1750 m).

spire and convex whorl, and the presence of nacre is an important difference.

The operculum of *Cirsonella* (Fig. 5E) differs from that of other genera in Skeneidae (*Skenea* Fleming, 1825; *Dikoleps* Hoisaeter, 1968; *Skeneoides* Warén, 1992, *Pseudorbis* Monterosato, 1884) in having the last whorl slowly tapering over about 1/3 of a whorl, while in the other Skeneidae it ends abruptly with an oblique edge covering about 1/20 of a whorl. Species of *Cirsonella* and *Seamountiella* typically retract the operculum only very shortly, or not at all, behind the peristome, contrary to most skeneids, because it abuts against a fold of the inner lip.

After the examination of over 1600 specimens and shells, we have been able to verify that the teleoconch of *Seamountiella* is developed in two phases: an initial phase of slow increase of the whorl diameter over a variable length,

with marked lines of growth interruption, and a second phase of rapid increase. *Seamountiella azorica* differs from the other known species in that the initial phase ranges between 1.5 and 2 whorls. In the sympatric *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp., it ranges between 0.7 and 1.2 whorls.

We have not seen a propodial penis in *Cirsonella* nor in *Seamountiella*. It may therefore be ventured that this genus could be more related to some turbinids, where in fact a similar radula and growth pattern of the operculum are common. Nevertheless, taking into account that *Seamountiella* n. gen. shares some anatomical, morphological and radular characters with *Cirsonella rometensis* (Fig. 5) as well as with *Skenea* (*S. serpuloides*) and *Dikoleps* (*D. cutleriana*), we tentatively place *Seamountiella* in Skeneidae until further molecular or soft part studies (ideally both) become available.

Seamountiella dimidia n. sp. (Figure 6A-C, 7A-F)

Type material: Holotype (spm, MNHN-IM-2000-34943) and 17 paratypes (s, MNHN-IM-2000-34944) from the type locality.

Material examined (2 spm, 743 s): Northeast Atlantic seamounts, SEAMOUNT 2. – Great Meteor Bank: 1 s, Stn DE174, 30°02.24'N, 28°42.42'W, 620 m. – Hyères Bank: 63 s, Stn DW182, 31°23.20'N, 28°53.50'W, 480 m; 4 s, Stn DW188, 31°30.00'N, 28°59.50'W, 310 m; 1 s, Stn DW192, 31°27.90'N, 28°59.10'W, 750 m; 9 s, Stn DW200, 31°19.10'N, 28°36.00'W, 1060 m; 210 s, Stn DW203, 31°09.50'N, 28°43.50'W, 845 m. – Atlantis Bank: 168 s, Stn DW255, 34°04.90'N, 30°15.30'W, 340 m; 104 s, Stn DW258, 33°59.8'N, 30°12.1'W, 420 m; 1 spm + 17 s, Stn DW263, 34°25.9'N, 30°32.5'W, 610 m (type material); 1 spm + 49 s, Stn DW 274, 34°05.13'N, 30°13.57'W, 280 m. – Irving Bank: 4 s, Stn DW231, 32°01.5'N, 27°54.5'W, 745 m; 60 s, Stn DW237, 32°15.9'N, 27°31.8'W, 670 m. – Plato Bank: 53 s, Stn DW242, 33°11.8'N, 28°57.0'W, 710 m.

Type locality: Atlantis Bank, 34°25.90'N-30°32.50'W, 610 m [Seamount 2, Stn DW263].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin adjective *dimidius*, -a, -um, meaning “of half”, alluding to that this species resembles *S. azorica* but it is about a half of the size.

Description: Shell very small (<2.6 mm), solid, smooth; spire depressed, obtuse at the apex, formed by 2.5-3.2 whorls separated by a weakly marked suture; not umbilicated. Shell white, shiny, with the subsutural and callus area more opaque.

Protoconch 0.75 whorl, smooth, of 260-280 μ m in maximum diameter. Teleoconch of up to 2.45 whorls, very convex at the periphery; last whorl occupying 97% of the total shell height.

Two differentiated growth phases are distinguishable: an initial phase of slow increase in diameter which extends for 0.7-1.2 whorls with well marked growth lines; and a second phase of rapid increasing of about 1.25 whorls, with much more subtle growth lines, only visible at the base, around the umbilical callus and close to the suture. Umbilicus completely covered by a callus; parietal perforation absent; callus not forming a channel.

Figure 6. *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp. A-C: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-34943), 2.1 mm in diameter, SEAMOUNT 2, Atlantis Bank, Stn DW263, 34°25.90'N, 30°32.50'W, 610 m.

Figura 6. *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp. A-C: holotipo (MNHN-IM-2000-34943), 2,1 mm de diámetro, SEAMOUNT 2, Atlantis Bank, Stn DW263, 34°25,90'N, 30°32,50'W, 610 m.

Aperture rounded, slightly prosocline, with a fold inside the inner lip, on which the operculum abuts; columella arched, thin, not reflected; outer lip not thickened, with a smooth, rounded edge.

Dimensions: the holotype measures 2.10 mm in diameter and 0.98 mm in height.

Distribution and bathymetric range: Only known from NE Atlantic seamounts: Great Meteor, Hyères, Irving,

Plato and Atlantis Banks, on bathyal bottoms between 280 and 1060 m.

Remarks: *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp. can be distinguished from *S. azorica* by its considerably smaller size, yet having the two differentiated growth phases and a rounded edge of the outer lip (thin and cutting in juveniles) indicating mature specimens. It also lacks any perforation in the parietal area of the umbilical callus.

Seamountiella caledonica n. sp. (Figure 8A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 8A-C) (MNHN-IM-2000-34945) and 1 paratype from the type locality (Figs. 8D-E) (MNHN-IM-2000-34946).

Material examined: only the type material.

Type locality: New Caledonia, Plateau des Chesterfield, 19°37'S, 158°43'E, 500-547 m [EBISCO: DW2601].

Etymology: The specific name refers to the archipelago where the species was collected.

Description: Shell small (<3.05 mm), solid, smooth; spire very depressed, obtuse at the apex, formed by up to 3.2 whorls, separated by a weakly marked suture; not umbilicated. Shell white

with two adapical reddish bands, the subsutural and basal area more opaque.

Protoconch of 0.75 whorl, smooth, of about 260 μ m in maximum diameter. Teleoconch of up to 2.4 whorls, very

Figure 7. *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp. from Atlantis Bank, SEAMOUNT 2 Stn DW263. A-C: paratypes (MNHN-IM-2000-34944), 2.45, 2.51, 2.58 mm in diameter; D-F: protoconchs.

Figura 7. *Seamountiella dimidia* n. sp. del Banco Atlantis, SEAMOUNT 2 Stn DW263. A-C: paratipos (MNHN-IM-2000-34944), 2,45, 2,51, 2,58 mm de diámetro; D-F: protoconchas.

convex at the periphery; the last whorl occupying about the 98% of the total shell height. Two differentiated growth phases can be observed: one initial

phase, which measures 1.3 whorls on the holotype, with slow increase in diameter, in which well marked growth lines are present; the other, a phase of

Figure 8. *Seamountiella caledonica* n. sp. from New Caledonia, Plateau des Chesterfield, Stn DW2601, 19°37'S, 158°43'E, 500-547 m. A-C: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-34945), 3.05 mm in diameter, D-E: paratype (MNHN-IM-2000-34946), 1.83 mm; F: protoconch.

Figura 8. Seamountiella caledonica n. sp. de Nueva Caledonia, Plateau des Chesterfield, Stn DW2601, 19°37'S, 158°43'E, 500-547 m. A-C: holotipo (MNHN-IM-2000-34945), 3,05 mm de diámetro; D-E: paratipo (MNHN-IM-2000-34946), 1,83 mm; F: protoconcha.

rapid increase in shell diameter, which measures 1.1 whorls with much more subtle growth lines that can be seen at the base, around the umbilical callus and close to the suture. Umbilicus completely covered by a callus; a small

parietal perforation present; callus not forming a channel.

Aperture oval, slightly prosocline, with a fold inside the inner lip. Columella arched, thin, reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thin, margin smooth.

Dimensions: the holotype is 3.05 mm in diameter and 1.6 mm in height.

Distribution and bathymetric range: Only known from the type locality in 500-547 m.

Remarks: The presence of two reddish colour bands distinguishes *S. caledonica* from any other species of the genus.

Seamountiella mayottensis n. sp. (Figure 9A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 9A) (MNHN-IM-2000-34947) and paratype (Fig. 9B) (MNHN-IM-2000-34948) from the type locality.

Material examined: only the type material.

Type locality: Mozambique Channel, Mayotte Island, NE of the North Reef, 12°29.9'S, 45°02'E, 450 m [BENTHEDI: Stn DS71].

Etymology: The specific name refers to the island where the species was collected.

Description: Shell small (<2.3 mm), solid, white hyaline, smooth, opaque and glossy; spire depressed, obtuse at the apex, formed by 3.25 whorls separated by a weakly marked suture; not umbilicated.

Protoconch of 0.75 whorls, smooth, of about 190-210 μm maximum diameter. Teleoconch of up to 2.5 whorls, very convex at the periphery; the last one occupying about the 97% of the total shell height. There are two distinct growth phases; an initial phase of slow increase in diameter, measuring just 0.5 whorls, with well marked growth lines, and a second phase of rapid increasing, of up to 2.0 whorls, with less evident growth lines.

Umbilicus completely covered by a thick callus; parietal perforation missing; callus forming a marked channel around its edge.

Aperture rounded, slightly prosocline, with a fold inside the inner lip; columella arched, thick, reflected; outer lip thin, smooth.

Dimensions: the holotype is 2.2 mm and the paratype is 2.26 mm in diameter.

Distribution and bathymetric range: Only known from the type locality. Bathyal, on coarse sands and organogenic gravels with pieces of sandstone in 450 m depth.

Remarks: *Seamountiella mayottensis* n. sp. can be distinguished from *S. azorica* by the smaller size of the protoconch (160-210 vs 260-290 μm , respectively); by having a very reduced initial growth stage; by lacking a parietal perforation in the callus, and by having a channel bordering the columella.

CONCLUSIONS

The placement of *Seamountiella* in the Skeneidae remains tentative. The current definition of Skeneidae is uncertain: HASZPRUNAR, KUNZE, BRÜCKNER & HEß (2016) stated: "It is ... difficult to define monophyletic Skeneidae by phenotypic characteristics... Despite that, all skeneid species investigated show a unique propodial penis". Admittedly *Seamountiella azorica* as well as *Cirsonella romettensis* lack this propodial penis, but more data are definitely needed before proposing a different family placement for those genera.

The growth pattern observed in *Seamountiella* species is puzzling, with a

teleoconch developed in two phases: a first phase of slow increase in diameter and variable length, characterized by the presence of marked lines of interrupted growth and a second phase of rapid increase. This results in an oval, rather than rounded, outline in apical view. This dual growth pattern might reflect a change in life history, but we have no clue to the origin of this abrupt change. The length of the second phase is similar in species studied from NE Atlantic Seamounts (*S. azorica*, *S. dimidia*) and measures 1.25 whorls, while it differs among the two Indo-

Figure 9. *Seamountiella mayottensis* n. sp. from Mayotte Island, NE of the North Reef, Benthedi Stn DS71. A: holotype, 2.2 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-34947); B, C: paratype, 2.26 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-34948); D, E: protoconch and detail of the paratype; F: protoconch of the holotype.

Figura 9. Seamountiella mayottensis n. sp. de la Isla de Mayotte, NE del Arrecife del Norte, Benthedi Stn DS71. A: *holotipo*, 2,2 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-34947); B, C: *paratipo*, 2,26 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-34947); D, E: *protoconcha* y *detalle del paratipo*; F: *protoconcha del holotipo*.

Pacific species examined (*S. mayottensis*: 2 whorls; *S. caledonica*: 1.1 whorls).

We have been examined a total of 62 live-taken specimens and 1672 shells from the NE Atlantic Seamounts, belonging to the two species (*Seamountiella azorica*, *S. dimidia*), and only 4 shells from Indo-Pacific (*S. mayottensis*, *S. caledonica*). The largest proportion (about 10%) of living specimens was collected on Galicia Bank (55 spm and 598 s of *S. azorica* only), whereas the number of living specimens was extremely low on the mid-Atlantic seamounts: Great Meteor Bank provided only 1 specimen, Hyères Bank 2 specimens and 460 s, followed by Atlantis bank with 1 specimen and 248 s, Irving Bank and Plato Bank with 127 and 139 s respectively. Where *S. azorica* and *S. dimidia* were found sympatrically, their bathymetric ranges are differentiated but overlapping: *Seamountiella dimidia* was found between 280 and 745 m, with also one occurrence at 1060 m, and *Seamountiella azorica* at greater depths, between 470 and 1520 m, although it is usually below 700 m; the

record at 470 m corresponds to a single specimen collected on the Great Meteor Bank, where the deeper steep slopes could not be sampled. In the Indian Ocean, *Seamountiella mayottensis* occurred at 450 m while the Pacific species *Seamountiella caledonica* was collected between 500-547 m.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BECK T., METZGER T. & FREIWALD A. 2006. *Biodiversity inventorial atlas (BIAS) of macrofaunal associations from OASIS seamount study sites*. Friedrich Alexander University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 125 pp.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1896. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse Alice 1888-1895. 1. Mollusques Gastropodes. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 9: 395-498, pls. 15-22.
- GOFAS S., LE RENARD J. & BOUCHET P. 2001. Mollusca. In: Costello M.J. et al. (eds), *European Register of Marine Species: a check-list of the marine species in Europe and a bibliography of guides to their identification*. Patrimoines Naturels, 50: 180-213.
- GRÜNDEL J. 2008. Remarks to the classification and phylogeny of the Ataphridae Cossmann, 1915 (Gastropoda, Archaeogastropoda) in the Jurassic. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 250 (2): 177-197.
- GRÜNDEL J. & KAIM A. 2006. Shallow-water gastropods from Late Oxfordian sands in Kleby (Pomerania, Poland). *Acta Geologica Polonica*, 56 (2): 121-157.
- KANO Y. 2008. Vetigastropod phylogeny and a new concept of Seguenzioidea: independent evolution of copulatory organs in the deep-sea habitats. *Zoologica Scripta*, 37: 1-21.
- HADLEY A. 2006. Combine ZP public domain image processing software. Available from <<https://web.archive.org/web/20160221032141/http://www.hadleyweb.pwp.blueyonder.co.uk/>>
- HASZPRUNAR G., KUNZE T., BRÜCKNER M. & HEB M. 2016. Towards a sound definition of Skeneidae (Mollusca, Vetigastropoda): 3D interactive anatomy of the type species, *Skenea serpuloides* (Montagu, 1808) and comments on related taxa. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution*, 16 (3): 577-595.
- HICKMAN C. S. & MCLEAN J.H. 1990. Systematic revision and suprageneric classification of trochacean gastropods. *Science Series of Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County*, 35: 1-169.
- HOFFMAN L. & FREIWALD A. 2017. A unique and diverse amalgamated mollusk assemblage from the Coral Patch Seamount, eastern Atlantic. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 7 (4): 61-79.

- HOFFMAN L., VAN HEUGTEN B. & LAVALEYE M. S.S. 2008. A new genus with four new species in the family Skeneidae (Gastropoda) from the Rockall Bank, northeastern Atlantic Ocean. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 3 (3): 39-48.
- LOCARD A. 1897-1898. Expéditions scientifiques du Travailleur et du Talisman pendant les années 1880, 1881, 1882 et 1883. *Mollusques testacés*. Paris, Masson. vol. 1 [1897], pp. 1-516 pls. 1-22; vol. 2 [1898], p. 1-515, pls. 1-18.
- RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2009. Sobre la posición sistemática de *Teinostoma azoricum* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. *Noticiario SEM*, 52: 55-56, fig. 1.
- SYSOEV A.V. 2014. Deep-sea fauna of European seas: An annotated species check-list of benthic invertebrates living deeper than 2000 m in the seas bordering Europe. Gastropoda. *Invertebrate Zoology*, 11 (1): 134-155.
- WARÉN A. 1992. New and little known "Skeneimorph" gastropods from the Mediterranean Sea and the adjacent Atlantic Ocean. *Bolletino Malacologico*, 27 (10-12): 149-248.
- WILLIAMS S.T. 2012. Advances in molecular systematics of the vetigastropod superfamily Trochoidea. *Zoologica Scripta*, 41: 571-595.
- ZELAYA D.G. 2004. The genus *Margarella* Thiele, 1893 (Gastropoda: Trochidae) in the southwestern Atlantic Ocean. *The Nautilus*, 118 (3): 112-120.

